

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

D6.3

**SYNTHESIS REPORT OF
DYNAMIC ACTION PLANS
FOR 41 MULTI-ACTOR
PLATFORMS**

APRIL 2022

SYNTHESIS REPORT OF DYNAMIC ACTION PLANS FOR 41 MULTI-ACTOR PLATFORMS

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1. Introduction

1.1. SHERPA and the Multi-Actor Platforms

SHERPA aims to gather relevant knowledge and opinions that contribute to the formulation of recommendations for future policies relevant to rural areas in the European Union. More specifically, the threefold objective of SHERPA is to:

- provide inputs for the design of future research policies, with a focus on preparation of work programmes under Horizon Europe;
- support the implementation of policies relevant to rural areas in the 2021-2027 programming period;
- support the setting of the direction of rural policy in the next programming period (after 2027).

SHERPA captures and uses results of on-going and past research projects (from FP6, FP7, H2020 and other EU funding streams) to engage civil society, policy-makers and scientists in the joint development of strategic thinking and practical recommendations for the formulation of policies relevant for rural areas.

The main tool through which the knowledge and opinions of stakeholders are collected is the Multi-Actor Platform (MAP). In SHERPA, Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) are **the rural interfaces that provide a forum for two-way exchanges of ideas for co-learning and co-creation of knowledge with actors at European and regional levels**. Each SHERPA MAP represents a local, regional or national network made of key subjects interested or operating in the context of rural areas. The composition of each MAP comprises a balanced representation from the three spheres of Society, Policy and Science. In addition, each MAP is supported by a Facilitator and a Monitor, who are in charge of running the MAPs and documenting the lessons learned.

21 SHERPA MAPs have been in operation in Phase 1 the project (between January 2020 and October 2021). In Phase 2 (2022-2023), 20 new MAPs added to the SHERPA count, for a total of **41 local, regional or national MAPs** established in 20 EU Member States, and **1 MAP at EU level**. Their objective is to engage citizens, researchers and policy-makers at local, national and EU levels in debates about future rural policies. Recommendations for developing modern rural policies at European, national and regional level, and concrete proposals for future research agendas, will be produced from the discussions within the MAPs. The position of the MAPs in the process of developing recommendations is shown in

Figure 1 (for a detailed illustration of the process, see Potters et al. 2021).

1.2. Dynamic Action Plans (DAPs)

Before the start of each MAP cycle, all the MAPs draw up a Dynamic Action Plan (DAP) to define and guide the MAP activities (see DAP template in Annex 1¹). The DAP illustrates the objectives, activities, expected outcomes and a time plan of the MAP for that year. It has multiple functions:

1. **Supporting** the establishment phase of the MAP, providing MAP members and Facilitators a space for starting an open dialogue, identifying common objectives and shared visions;
2. **Planning** activities for a given period, in a dynamic and flexible manner;

¹ Since the second MAP cycle, the DAP was simplified and shortened, in order to facilitate its usage and to reduce the workload required to facilitators.

3. **Communicating** about the MAP.

According to the principles adopted in SHERPA, the DAPs are characterised by a *flexible* programming for both content and timing; are *co-constructed* within each MAP maintaining discussion and dialogue with representatives of Society, Policy and Research; and involve *multi-level interactions* as EU level policy issues will be discussed to formulate specific recommendations for future EU research agendas and rural policies. This dynamic approach allows the MAPs to find their own way of co-constructing and refining strategies and activities according to their specific needs.

Figure 1 - The SHERPA process. Source: Potters et al., 2021.

1.3. **Purpose of the document**

The aim of this report (deliverable 6.3) is to provide an updated overview and systematic synthesis of key information from both 21 MAPs in operation since Phase 1 and 20 newly established MAPs. This synthesis is based upon the Dynamic Action Plans (DAPs) compiled by each MAP between December 2021 and February 2022, and collects the main elements related to the objectives, activities, and outcomes that the MAPs plan to address in Phase 2 of SHERPA.

Currently, at month 31 (April 2022), the 41 MAPs are at different degrees of development. The 21 MAPs are approaching their third cycle and rely on two years of experience with the SHERPA process. New MAPs are being established and/or preparing for starting their activities.

This document aims also to provide an overall understanding of the role of the MAPs in SHERPA and how they are contributing towards achieving the objectives of the project.

2. SHERPA Multi Actor-Platforms

2.1. Overview of the 41 MAPs

In 2022, 20 new MAPs were established in addition to the 21 MAPs (Figure 2) already in place since two years (early 2020).

Most of the new MAPs (17) are being established in countries which have been hosting one or more SHERPA MAPs since 2020, namely in: Bulgaria, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Portugal, the Netherlands, Romania. The 3 new MAPs established in Belgium, Estonia and Sweden are instead the first experience of SHERPA platforms in these countries.

All SHERPA platforms will be working on policy issues relating to rural areas. Table 1 displays the distribution of the MAPs across partner countries, geographical area and scope of the MAP.

Figure 2 – Map of the locations of current and new Multi-Actor Platforms .

Table 1 - List of the 41 MAPs, including country (in alphabetical order), name, geographical area and topic selected for the third MAP cycle (cf. table 2). New MAPs are indicated in green.

Country	Name of the MAP	Geographical area/scope
BELGIUM	MAP Atelier Centre Wallonie	Wallonia, regional
BULGARIA	MAP Rural Mapping Bulgaria	Bulgaria, national
BULGARIA	MAP Social infrastructure	Bulgaria, national
CZECH REPUBLIC	MAP VENUS	Moravian-Silesian Region, Opava, regional
CZECH REPUBLIC	MAP Climate Friendly Village (CFV)	Czech Republic, national
DENMARK	MAP Denmark	Denmark, national
ESTONIA	MAP Estonia	Estonia, national
FINLAND	MAP Suomi	Finland, national
FRANCE	MAP PACA Sud	Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur, sub-regional
FRANCE	MAP Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée	Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée, regional
GERMANY	MAP Schleswig Holstein	Schleswig Holstein, regional
GERMANY	MAP Nienburg	Nienburg county, sub-regional
GREECE	MAP South Aegean	Syros, South Aegean, regional
GREECE	MAP Central Greece	Central Greece, regional
GREECE	MAP Peloponnese	Peloponnese peninsula in southern Greece, regional
HUNGARY	MAP Hungarian AKIS	Hungary, national
HUNGARY	MAP Land use planning for climate	Hungary, national
HUNGARY	MAP Rural prosperity	Hungary, national
ITALY	MAP Tuscany	Rural areas of Tuscany, regional
ITALY	MAP Casentino	Casentino area, sub-regional
ITALY	MAP Montagna Toscana (MOVING)	Mountain areas of northern Tuscany, sub-regional
ITALY	MAP Emilia Romagna	Emilia Romagna, regional
LITHUANIA	MAP Circular Bio-economy (CBioLit)	Lithuania, national
NETHERLANDS	MAP Greenport Gelderland	River area of the Gelderland province in The Netherlands, regional
NETHERLANDS	MAP Vital villages	Northern provinces Friesland, Groningen, Drenthe
NETHERLANDS	MAP Climate proof ruralities (P10 network)	Rural municipalities in The Netherlands, national
POLAND	MAP Zielone Sąsiedztwo	Mazowieckie, sub-regional
POLAND	MAP Zachodniopomorskie	Zachodniopomorskie, regional
POLAND	MAP Bieszczady	Podkarpackie Voivodship, regional
PORTUGAL	MAP Alqueva	Alentejo, regional
PORTUGAL	MAP Rural Portugal	Centro-Region, regional
PORTUGAL	MAP SW Alentejo	Southwest Alentejo, sub-regional
ROMANIA	MAP Rural Transylvania	West, Nord-West and Central regions of Romania, regional
ROMANIA	MAP Iași	Iași county, regional

ROMANIA	MAP Argeş	Argeş county, regional
SLOVENIA	MAP SVARUN - Slovenian Agricultural and Rural Network for Dialogue	Slovenia, national
SPAIN	MAP IDRA - Innovación en Desarrollo Rural de Aragón	Aragon, regional
SPAIN	MAP Galician Rural Interfaces	Galicia, regional
SWEDEN	MAP Norbotten	Norbotten, regional
UNITED KINGDOM	MAP Dee Catchment Partnership	Basin of River Dee, Scotland, sub-regional
UNITED KINGDOM	MAP Rural Scotland	Scotland, regional

2.2. Topics for the third MAP cycle

The SHERPA project produces policy recommendations based on specific topics that are deemed relevant to rural areas. Following the process depicted in Figure 1, the topic(s) are selected at the onset of each MAP cycle, by drawing from the broader ongoing EU policy debate and the interests of the MAPs. The detail of the topics addressed by the MAPs in the past and current MAP cycles is illustrated in **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference..** Whereas in the first MAP cycle all the MAPs undertook a reflection on the Long Term Vision for Rural Areas² of the EU, in the second cycle an internal consultation brought to the definition of three different topics, along which the MAPs were equally distributed. In preparation for the third cycle, the MAPs were invited to select among four different topics, emerged from previous discussions. The result is less balanced in terms of the MAPs distribution, compared to the previous cycle: nine MAPs have selected Topic 1; four MAPs have selected Topic 2, while Topic 3 and 4 have been selected by respectively twelve and sixteen MAPs (Table 3).

Table 2 – Topics addressed by the MAP in the three MAP cycle. A fourth and final cycle is planned in 2023.

Phase 1		Phase 2	
MAP cycle 1 (2020)	MAP cycle 2 (2021)	MAP cycle 3 (2022)	MAP cycle 4 (2023)
TOPIC 1. Long term vision for rural areas (LTVRA)	<p>TOPIC 1. Change in production and diversification of the rural economy</p> <p>TOPIC 2. Climate change and environmental services</p> <p>TOPIC 3. Foresight exercise – Alternative rural futures: how to get there?</p>	<p>TOPIC 1. Social dimension of rural areas</p> <p>TOPIC 2. Digitalisation and smart ruralities</p> <p>TOPIC 3. Land-use management in the context of climate change</p> <p>TOPIC 4. Entrepreneurship, social economy, just transition and sustainable value chains</p>	TOPIC 1- Governance (forthcoming)

² The work done by each SHERPA MAP on the LTVRA is synthesised in the MAPs Position Papers available here. These documents (all available [here](#)) fed into the SHERPA Position Paper on the LTVRA (Chartier et al., 2020) and represent the contribution of SHERPA MAPs to the consultations on the LTVRA launched by the EU Commission in the late 2019.

Table 3 - MAPs' distribution along the 4 topics selected for the third cycle

Social dimension of rural areas	Digitalisation and smart ruralities	Land-use management in the context of climate change	Entrepreneurship, social economy, just transition and sustainable value chains
MAP Atelier Centre Wallonie MAP Social infrastructure MAP Estonia MAP Vital villages MAP Bieszczady MAP SW Alentejo MAP SVARUN MAP IDRA MAP Galician Rural Interfaces	MAP Suomi MAP Hungarian AKIS MAP Rural Portugal MAP Norbotten	MAP VENUS MAP Climate Friendly Village MAP Denmark MAP PACA Sud MAP Rural Policy for Environment MAP Hungarian Land use planning for climate MAP Greenport Gelderland MAP Climate proof ruralities MAP Zachodniopomorskie MAP Alqueva MAP Dee Catchment Partnership MAP Rural Scotland	MAP Rural Mapping Bulgaria MAP Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée MAP Nienburg MAP South Aegean MAP Central Greece MAP Peloponnese MAP Rural prosperity Tuscany MAP MAP Casentino MAP Montagna Toscana MAP Emilia Romagna MAP Circular Bio-economy MAP Zielone Sąsiedztwo MAP Rural Transylvania MAP Iași MAP Arges

2.3. Getting to know the Multi-Actor Platforms

In this section, each Multi-Actor Platform is presented in more detail. Each MAP’s self-introductory paragraph includes main information about the MAP’s focus on the topic selected, the location and scope, and contact details of the MAP Facilitator, to whom enquiries can be addressed for further information. The list below starts with the newly established MAPs and continues with the MAPs that have been in operation since Phase I of SHERPA, in alphabetical order by country.

BELGIUM – MAP Atelier Centre Wallonie

The MAP is based in Belgium, Wallonia. Its creation is supported by R.E.D., an international and non-profit organisation with members and partners across Europe. R.E.D. is a major actor in the Greater Region on issues related to rurality and has launched several platforms of organisations and actors in the rural world. It has also been an active player since several decades making political proposals for rural areas. It promotes continuous exchanges on rural policies and their implementation with the dual purpose of a better operationality in the field and enhanced dialogue with the European, regional and local institutions. The MAP Atelier Sherpa Wallonie will focus on the Walloon region through a bottom-up approach and its network will build on territorial development experiences. The selected topic is the “social dimension of rural areas”, related to the area of action 'Stronger rural areas' of the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas.

For detailed information contact facilitator: Bérénice Dupeux Berenice.Dupeux@ecorys.com

BULGARIA – MAP Social infrastructure

The MAP will focus on discussing the contribution of social infrastructure and social policy in rural areas, as key pillars to provide a viable livelihood. The MAP is meant to start a debate on the adoption of new policies for stimulating rural regions and implementing best practices of innovative social models in line with contemporary needs. The purpose of this discussion will be to make recommendations to policy-makers on these issues, to enable the realisation of the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas in the region by 2040. Related

issues will be discussed in connection with opportunities available to rural areas for a better and more prosperous future.

For detailed information contact facilitator: Mihaela Mihailova m.mihailova92@gmail.com

CZECH REPUBLIC – MAP Climate Friendly Village (CFV)

Within the topic of Land-use management in the context of climate change (topic 3), MAP CFV will focus on planting permanent greenery in the landscape, which reduces the impacts of climate change and can affect municipalities and LAGs in the Czech Republic. This MAP has been in operation since 2021, having formulated a list of 10 activities that the municipality can do for achieving climate sustainability. In 2022, MAP CFV will be focusing on a selected theme from the 10 points list, namely the creation and preservation of sustainable (agricultural) landscapes. Earlier dialogue between stakeholders revealed that the need for a diverse landscape is acknowledged, but few are willing to do anything for it. MAP CFV will explore the problem more in depth in Phase II, to understand whether lack of local power (local human resources, ready potentials) and/or weak conditional power (financial, political/jurisdictional and scientific support from centre) constrain the change of landscape. The aim is to find out what are the opportunities and barriers for creating resilient landscapes in times of climate change.

For detailed information contact facilitator: Vít Hrdoušek hrdousek.v@straznicko.cz

ESTONIA – MAP Estonia

Based on consultation with the MAP Estonia members, the thematic focus for the first MAP cycle is “social dimension of rural areas” (topic 1). The Estonian MAP members have indicated this theme as relevant in order to explore how to attract young people to the countryside and create attractive jobs in the rural areas. These topics are linked to the keywords: social inclusion, poverty reduction, well-being and related to the area of action ‘stronger rural areas’ of the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas.

For detailed information contact facilitator: Anne-Liisi Mändmets anne-liisi.mandmets@agri.ee

FRANCE – MAP Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée

The MAP Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée will be coordinated by the CIHEAM Montpellier with the support of the Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée Local Action Group (LAG). The selected topic is “entrepreneurship, social economy, just transition and sustainable value chains” (topic 4), and more specifically territorialised food systems.

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GERMANY – MAP Nienburg

The MAP in Nienburg has been established in 2019 in the H2020 project, UNISECO, with the aim to co-construct strategies for promoting the implementation of agro-ecological approaches that address the identified key sustainability issues of the region such as biodiversity loss and improvements in water quality. Recommendations were derived as to how the implementation of agro-ecological practices can be initiated and enhanced and the sustainability of farming systems strengthened. The members of the MAP in the country Nienburg in Lower Saxony (Germany) co-constructed a series of actions that can be pursued by local actors to stimulate the creation of markets that recognise the value that agro-ecological practices provide to society as well as the additional efforts of farmers. At the end of the H2020 UNISECO project, MAP members expressed their interest in continuing the engagement to follow up on the co-constructed recommendations and to develop concrete actions and solutions for sustainable value chains. In addition to the UNISECO

project, this MAP will build on findings of the DiverIMPACTS project and consider findings from a number of other ongoing Horizon 2020 projects such as ALL-Ready, CONSOLE and FOODSHIFT 2030.

For detailed information contact facilitator: Gerald Schwarz gerald.schwarz@thuener.de

GREECE – MAP Central Greece

Central Greece is one of the least populated geographical regions of Greece and the second largest in terms of total area of the country (a territory of 15 561 km² with 555 761 inhabitants). It is well known for its rich natural resources, cultural heritage, and historical monuments, while a large number of the region's enterprises in the food industry are mainly engaged in the processing of agricultural products. Central Greece is generating 4.7% of the National GDP being the fifth largest regional economy in Greece. Its development level, in terms of GDP per capita, is close to the national average (90%), but very low compared to the EU average (60%). The region is an important agricultural zone, and farming represents a significant portion of the regional economic activity, with sizable growth potential, if combined with modern Information and Communications Technology (ICT) tools. Tourism is a key source of income and employment and is included among the fastest growing service activities, although being underdeveloped still (only 1.06% of the country's tourism revenues were from Central Greece in 2016-2020). Looking at the overall performance of the selected region (RIS3 Regional Assessment) and considering the relevant literature and consultations with MAP members, the main issues to be discussed in the third MAP cycle will relate to employment, reskilling, upskilling, entrepreneurship, short supply chains/sustainable value chains (topic 4).

For detailed information contact facilitator: Olga Kriezi olgakrie@gmail.com

GREECE – MAP Peloponnese

The Peloponnese peninsula in southern Greece covers 15 490 km² (11.7% of the total Greek land area) with a mountainous interior and deeply indented coasts. The region has 577 903 (2011) inhabitants, producing 5.34% of the National GDP in 2015. The region has a strong manufacturing base, an important agricultural production, but the majority of activity is in services including tourism, which has a growth potential given recent public and private investments. The regional innovation system is rather weak and regional enterprises are not well served in terms of more specialist market and technological advice. The scientific focus of the regional higher education research institutes in natural sciences is coherent with the regional economic specialisation. Looking at the overall performance of the selected region (RIS3 Regional Assessment) and considering the relevant literature and consultations with MAP members, the main issues to be discussed in the third MAP cycle will relate to employment, reskilling, upskilling, entrepreneurship, short supply chains/sustainable value chains (topic 4).

For detailed information contact facilitator: Nicoleta Darra nicoletadarra@aua.gr

HUNGARY – MAP Land use planning for climate neutrality

The main challenge is the need for optimal land-use ratios and techniques that simultaneously ensure the production of competitive and quality food raw materials, as well as climate-neutral solutions. This topic is a follow-up of the topic "Climate change and environmental services" covered by seven MAPs in 2021 and corresponds to the area of action 'More resilient rural areas that foster well-being' of the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas. It covers issues related to climate change and mitigation through land-use planning and management. The Hungarian Land-use planning for climate neutrality MAP covers geographically the whole country, as on the one hand, Hungary is considered a region by the EU rural development policy, and on the other hand, the topic itself is a horizontal issue. The MAP is made up of selected members of the "Agri-Environment and Climate" subgroup set up by the Ministry of Agriculture to support CAP strategic planning. In line with the relevant SHERPA Discussion Paper, the MAP examines the necessary transitions in rural areas in achieving the EU Green Deal and climate neutrality goals by analysing Hungarian specificities.

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HUNGARY – MAP Rural prosperity

The Hungarian Rural Prosperity MAP covers geographically the whole country as on the one hand, due to its size Hungary is considered one region in several policy aspects and on the other hand, according to the different typologies, a significant proportion of the country's territory is rural area with lower population density, often with a strong agricultural character. The MAP is expected to have the greatest impact if the territory is not further subdivided. The relevance of the topic selected (Entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition, including sustainable value chains) is justified also by the fact that it is embedded into the CAP strategic planning, thus it requires the cooperation of policy-makers, researchers, entrepreneurs/farmers, and members of the civilian sector or in broader context the society with various stakeholders. The MAP's core group is the CAP Pillar II sub-working group established by the Ministry of Agriculture to facilitate the CAP strategic planning process. The MAP will carry out situation analysis and needs assessment regarding employment, development of human resources (i.e. reskilling, upskilling), business and social entrepreneurship, and sustainable value chains and it will propose suitable policy solutions.

For detailed information contact facilitator: Csaba Bálint balint.csaba@aki.gov.hu

ITALY – MAP Casentino

This MAP has been initiated ex-novo, from the informal – and separate – initiative of two mayors from the Casentino area together with researchers from the University of Pisa. Several meetings were held to understand commonalities and opportunities for joining efforts (with UNIPI proposing the MAP as a space and work method). MAP Casentino refers to an area geographically identified by the Casentino Valley, in the Eastern part of Tuscany. The area is affected by depopulation, youth outmigration and difficult access to basic services. As such, it has been among the 72 inner areas identified as pilots by the SNAI policy. However, many opportunities can be identified, which are related to a well-developed agricultural sector and manufacturing industry. Many protected areas and a large wooded area designated as the National Park "Foreste Casentinesi" make it an attractive tourism destination. MAP Casentino will address the topic 4 on "entrepreneurship, the social economy, just transition and sustainable value chains". Being one of the three MAPs activated in Tuscany, MAP Casentino will be involved in the round of talks and activities in preparation for to the Regional Conference on Agriculture, which will be held in Tuscany in Spring 2022.

For detailed information contact facilitator: Sabrina Arcuri sabrina.arcuri@agr.unipi.it

ITALY – MAP Montagna Toscana (MOVING)

Based on consultations made during the previous MAP cycle and opportunities for synergies with the H2020 sister project, MOVING, operating in the same area, the MAP Montagna Toscana-MOVING will focus on topic 4, with particular reference to sustainable agri-food value chains. The MAP has a sub-regional scope, though covering a broad mountainous area across three different provinces (Lucca, Massa-Carrara and Pistoia) and different localities with their own identity, namely: Garfagnana, Media Valle del Serchio, Alta Versilia, Lunigiana and Appennino Pistoiese. The whole area is affected by issues related to depopulation, low access to basic services, ageing, and loss of economic activity. The H2020 project MOVING has been operating in the area through its own MAP, the activities of which pertain to the sustainability of mountain value chains. MOVING activities in the area have been so far focused in the locality of Alta Versilia, although the need for exchanges and networking across the locality's boundaries has emerged. Being one of the three MAPs activated in Tuscany, the Montagna Toscana-MOVING MAP will be involved in the round of talks and activities in preparation for to the Regional Conference on Agriculture, which will be held in Tuscany in Spring 2022.

For detailed information contact facilitator: Sabrina Tomasi sabrina.tomasi89@gmail.com

The NETHERLANDS – MAP Vital villages

The MAP Vital villages is situated in the three northern provinces of the Netherlands: Friesland, Groningen, Drenthe. The MAP is established in close collaboration with the KKNN (Knowledge Network Population Decline Northern Netherlands). The aim of the KKNN is to bring together knowledge on demographic change in the northern parts of the Netherlands. The theme of the MAP is “Vital Villages, Liveable Rural Areas” and the MAP aims to strengthen meaningful connections between rural reality on the ground with policy reality. The purpose is to contribute to policies that can better support the conservation and improvement of liveable rural areas as it is experienced and valued by the diversity of rural inhabitants. In order to reach this aim, the MAP brings together societal actors working on the ground in different villages with variety of methods to engage local inhabitants in rural development, with policy actors at municipal and provincial levels. Selected researchers from RUG, WUR and Hanze Hogeschool will participate to bring a broad perspective and deepen the dialogue. The MAP dialogue will start with informal conversations with societal actors to set the focus and design of the MAP dialogue. An inventory among MAP members helps to get overview of experiences and priorities. The actual dialogue will consist of two rounds, the first one before the summer aiming to share a diversity of experiences and perspectives: What liveability aspects are considered relevant and important by inhabitants of rural areas? What is needed to maintain or improve liveability in rural areas for their inhabitants (in terms of process and content)? How can policy better support this? The second MAP meeting will aim to come to a joint view and draft the MAP Position Paper.

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The NETHERLANDS – MAP Climate proof ruralities (P10 network)

The MAP focusses on climate adaptation and aims to contribute to increasing awareness on climate adaptation in rural areas. P10 is a network of large rural municipalities in the Netherlands. This network has been established in 2008 and currently consists of 30 members. The P10-municipalities are characterised by a large area of land and the absence of an urban core. These characteristics make that these municipalities often encounter similar challenges and tasks when preserving the quality of life and vitality of the area. The P10 has developed a Rural Agenda to draw attention to the challenges on the countryside. In addition, the agenda also provides a perspective on finding solutions for future challenges in which they urge city and countryside to work together, thus connecting urban and rural areas. A few examples of the issues on the P10 Rural Agenda are the energy transition, climate change, healthcare and housing. The P10 works alongside four overall program lines, in which they elaborate the challenges and opportunities of their rural members. These four overall programs are vital, social, sustainable and supportive rural areas. Every program line contains of several small thematic working groups. The program line ‘Sustainable rural areas’ includes issues such as climate change and climate adaptation. The P10 urges for more regional and local approaches and multi-level governance involvement in national policy issues. For this reason, the area-specific approach is supported and highlighted during this MAP dialogue. Since there is no working group on climate adaptation yet within the P10, this MAP dialogue could also contribute to bring interested participants together and discuss the possibilities of creating a working group on this topic in the future.

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POLAND – MAP Zachodniopomorskie

The MAP Zachodniopomorskie will focus on analysing contemporary trends in land use and identifying relationships between climate change and land use and related land management practices in the Zachodniopomorskie region. The aim of the discussion will be to develop recommendations for decision makers on directions for supporting land use management to enhance adaptation and mitigation of climate changes in the region. This will enable the creation of a common long-term vision for building resilience, adaptive capacity, and transformation of rural communities.

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POLAND – MAP Bieszczady

The Bieszczady MAP area is located in the Podkarpackie Voivodship, in southeastern Poland and includes part of the Eastern Carpathians (the Bieszczady Mountains) and the Bieszczady National Park. It covers an area of two districts (Leski, Bieszczadzki). It is a borderland of the European Union (Polish-Ukrainian border) that is why this region is ethnically diverse. The inhabitants have Polish, Ukrainian and Boyko roots. The Bieszczady county is the most sparsely populated area in Poland, for many years neglected and far from large urban centres. One of the key problems of this region is the highest unemployment rate in Poland (Leski District: 16.7%, Bieszczadzki District: 14.9%, compared to Poland: 6.2% at the end of 2020), the quality of life, negative migration balance, isolation, poverty.

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PORTUGAL – MAP SW Alentejo

The area of Southwest Alentejo (SW) is marked by agricultural activities developed in the Mira Irrigation Perimeter (public irrigation), which was "overlapped" by a Natural Park. Agricultural activities are mainly focused on the production of vegetables and berries (in plastic greenhouses), with a strong foreign investment and with a high need of labour. This labour has been mainly obtained through immigrants from Asian countries (Thailand, Nepal, India, Bangladesh, etc.), which has created a set of new challenges for the region. Despite the recent exposure of several situations of improper accommodation of people, the region has been an example in the integration of immigrants. In any case, it is essential to deepen the discussion on the social issues associated with the region's development.

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ROMANIA – MAP Iași

In Romania, the European Rural Development Network (ERDN) – Institute of Agricultural Economics of the Romanian Academy coordinates the Multi-Actor Platform that operates in NUTS III level regions Iași of the country. The Romanian Institute of Agricultural Economics facilitates the activities of the platform. Main challenges in rural areas of Iași county are the dual structure of farming system (small number of very large holdings and prevalence of small farms), demographic shift, labour shortages, low integration of local farmers on food chains, lack of cooperation among farmers. The platform aims to improve the value added of farming and agri-food activities by supporting the building of sustainable short food supply chains valorising the rural-urban linkages and fructifying the opportunities generated by the appetite of consumers on local agri-food products.

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ROMANIA – MAP Argeş

In Romania, the European Rural Development Network (ERDN) – Institute of Agricultural Economics of the Romanian Academy coordinates the Multi-Actor Platform that operates in NUTS III level regions Argeş of the country. The Romanian Institute of Agricultural Economics facilitates the activities of the platform. Main challenges in rural areas of Argeş county are the labour and technological shortages, low diversification of rural economy, fragmentation of land operation, lack of cooperation and market integration of local producers. The platform aims to support prosperity of rural areas, with a special focus on mountain and hilly communities, through building of local environment that support sustainable and resilient rural development and integration of rural local economy' actors in sustainable value chains.

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SWEDEN – MAP Norrbotten

Based on consultation with the MAP Norrbotten members, the thematic focus for the third MAP cycle is topic 2 on 'digitalisation, smart ruralities, including rural-urban relations'. In Norrbotten this include sustainable place-based development, skills and competence, smart ruralities, smartly adapted digital development, justice (between rural actors and between urban-rural areas). The MAP Norrbotten is geographically focused on Norrbotten, one of 21 regions in Sweden. It is a large and varied region, based in the northernmost part of Sweden, spanning over 97 000 km² (which is the size of Austria), and having a coastline, vast forests, and mountainous areas. Norrbotten has about 250 000 permanent inhabitants. The region borders to both Norway and Finland, which indicate additional inhabitants that commute for work and tourism as voluntary temporary inhabitants throughout the year. The largest concentration of permanent inhabitants and workplaces are along the coast, in Piteå, Luleå and Kalix. More than half of the inhabitants (170 000 inhabitants) live within commuting distance to the city Luleå. Norrbotten is rich in both material and immaterial resources, including Sami and Swedish cultures and languages, mountains, biodiversity, silence, polar nights, northern lights, and midnight sun, forests, minerals, mining, forestry, and farming.

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Below, the 21 MAPs in operation since Phase I of SHERPA are described.

BULGARIA – MAP Rural Mapping Bulgaria

In the third cycle of MAP Rural Mapping Bulgaria will focus on discussing the contribution of bioeconomy value chain for rural development, comprising the public policy in bioeconomy and the potential for adoption of bioeconomy to rural economic value chains. The purpose of this discussion will be to make recommendations to policy-makers on these issues, enabling the realization of the vision for rural areas in the region in 2040. This was presented by the members of the MAP in the document on the position of the MAP for the first cycle of the MAP and the issues addressed regarding diversification of the rural economy, as discussed in the second cycle of the MAP.

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CZECH REPUBLIC – MAP Venus

MAP VENUS has focused on the implementation of measures to reduce the impacts of climate change through systemic support for the implementation of energy saving measures, more economical use of energy sources and increasing the share of sustainable energy sources in the region. One of the tools for the implementation of the climate and energy objectives of rural areas is the promotion and building of energy communities as presented in Article 22 of Directive (EU) 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable

sources (RED II Directive). By the end of 2021, energy issues became the focus of attention of citizens, media and politicians due to global, European and national events that have resulted in the decline of many energy suppliers in the Czech Republic. One of the hidden problems – the vulnerability of end-users of energy (companies and households) – has been fully exposed (the bankruptcy of suppliers has affected about 1 million customers in the country). The process of bankruptcy of suppliers has not yet been stopped and it may continue in 2022. The subsequent jump in the price (up to 400%) of energy and energy raw materials was only the culmination of a long-term process, which has many causes and several foreseeable consequences. Fears of the threat of energy poverty for the population and a reduction in the competitiveness of businesses are coming true, with the danger of a deepening of the economic crisis with all its consequences, including unemployment. An unforeseen advantage of this crisis situation is the massive increase in the interest of residents, companies, businesses, public administration and municipalities in renewable energy sources; the implementation of energy saving measures and the interest in agreements at the level of local energy communities, whose members are interested in local cooperation, energy exchange and building community energy (as MAP VENUS has been predicting, preparing and directing for several years). Similar associations and cooperatives in Western Europe were the inspiration for the creation of the energy community in Opava region.

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DENMARK – MAP Denmark

In Denmark, NordRegio coordinates the MAP Denmark, which operates at the national level. This platform is based on the Rural Joint Council of Denmark with members from national organisations, municipalities and civil society. Possible topics to be addressed are population, settlements, business, employment, (digital) infrastructure, education, and health. The MAP aims to formulate clear feedback and positions on the themes it discussed in the MAP, such as qualifying the EU understanding of the situation in the Danish rural areas as well as the needs for policy regulation, support and research. Based on consultation with the MAP Denmark members, the thematic focus for the third MAP cycle is “Land-use planning in the context of climate change” (topic 3).

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FINLAND – MAP Suomi

During 2022, the main thematic focus of the Finnish MAP will be on “digitalisation and smart ruralities” (topic 2). This theme was selected based on a survey that was sent to the Finnish MAP, where MAP members were asked to rank the four suggested themes by the project from the most interesting to least interesting. Among the four alternatives, this theme gained the most support. The topic is of central importance for rural policy and development in Finland and it was partially addressed by the Finnish MAP already in 2021. In the Finnish MAP’s Position Paper dealing with Diversification of the rural economy, one of the three sub-themes examined was Smart rurality, smart communities and digitalisation. Here, aspects such as smart adaptation, smart villages and remote work were highlighted, and they have emerged on the rural policy agenda in Finland in recent years and been further propelled by the Covid-19 pandemic. The more specific thematic focus for 2022 will be discussed and agreed upon together with the MAP members.

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FRANCE – MAP PACA Sud

After exchanging with the members of the platform, and taking into account the results of the first two cycles and the consortium's thematic proposals, two topics were selected that are linked to one another: i) land-use management in the context of climate change: the discussions during the second phase showed that the issue of the adaptation of rural territories to climate change is a major issue in the context of the implementation of the new French resilience-climate law and makes it possible to address many of the priorities identified in our previous work; and ii) entrepreneurship, social economy, just transition and sustainable value chains, which is complementary and may allow a more programmatic approach that addresses the next LEADER call for proposals.

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GERMANY – MAP Schleswig-Holstein

The agri-food sector in the Schleswig-Holstein region generates benefits for the regional economy but it is also contributing to a number of environmental issues. The latter include the loss of biodiversity, water quality and eutrophication, wind and soil erosion caused by climate change and increasing flood hazard in coastal areas. Further challenges relate to land use competition and structural change in agriculture. Agricultural land is converted to housing and transport infrastructure uses, and to a smaller extent for reforestation and for ecological compensation measures. These key issues are also reflected in the Rural Development Programme for Schleswig-Holstein, which focuses on the priority areas of restoring, preserving and enhancing ecosystems related to agriculture and forestry, social inclusion and local development in rural areas, and to improve structures including a coast protection plan with support for flood protection. A key focus in previous discussions was on innovative approaches agri-environmental measures and other rural development measures that foster social and human capital of rural communities and ensure an adequate remuneration of wider ecosystem services provided by land managers. Specifically, the thematic focus of the third cycle of MAP's activities will be on land-use management in the context of climate change, with the aim to further elaborate on practical solutions and recommendations for innovative agri-environmental measures and other measures in the rural development programme post 2027.

For more information contact facilitator: Gerald Schwarz gerald.schwarz@thueneren.de

GREECE – MAP South Aegean

The South Aegean MAP operates at the regional level and the Region of South Aegean is the central actor in the platform. This region is characterised by its traditional economy, low levels of education and high degree of unemployment and depopulation. The MAP has been working on the development of sustainable policies in the region's specific sectors, the adoption of technology adoption and innovative environmentally friendly policies. The objective of the MAP is to promote innovation and digital transformation, and foster socio-economic rural development. Based on consultations with the MAP members the region, the thematic focus of the MAP in the third cycle will be "entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition, including sustainable value chains" (topic 4).

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HUNGARY – MAP Hungarian AKIS

The Hungarian AKIS MAP covers geographically the whole country as on the one hand due to its size Hungary is considered one region in several policy aspects and on the other hand the topic itself – Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System is a horizontal issue. The MAP is expected to have the greatest impact if the territory is not further subdivided. The relevance of the topic is justified also by the fact that it is

embedded into the CAP strategic planning, thus it requires the cooperation of policy makers, researchers and farmers or in broader context the society with various stakeholders. The MAP's core group is the AKIS sub-working group established by the Ministry of Agriculture to facilitate the CAP strategic planning process. The sub-working groups activities supplement, however, the activities of an AKIS group established originally by the Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture and re-established by the Chamber and the Ministry of Agriculture last year with a broad and more general focus.

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ITALY – MAP Tuscany

The regional MAP Tuscany will address, for the year 2022, the topic no. 4 on 'Entrepreneurship, the social economy, just transition and sustainable value chains'. In particular, considering that two new MAPs are currently being established in Tuscany at the sub-regional level, the regional MAP will work as an umbrella MAP. It will provide both a space for broader exchange and networking and an opportunity to address common issues at a higher level of governance. The rationale behind the selection of one common topic for all the 3 MAPs is meant to facilitate exchange and learning, help maintain the focus and make synergies (while ensuring a certain degree of diversity at each MAP's level). Across the region, there is an ongoing debate involving actors from many different localities on topics related to the revitalisation of rural areas with a particular focus on mountain areas, but also in relation to the tools of governance which may support entrepreneurship in the agri-food sector and the whole territory at large (food communities, rural districts, local food strategies, etc.).

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ITALY – MAP Emilia-Romagna

The agri-food sector in Emilia-Romagna generates significant benefits for regional and national economy but is also causing a high territorial fragmentation, land use change and intensification that negatively affect biodiversity. Moreover, climate variability is increasing the risk of drought for regional agriculture that is likely to undergo significant changes in the coming years. Given that, the Emilia-Romagna MAP is mostly focused on discussing innovative solutions that can sustain the competitiveness of the sector while enhancing environmental protection and increasing the sustainability of productions. Specifically, the thematic focus of the third cycle of MAP's activities is on "land-use management in the context of climate change" (topic 3).

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LITHUANIA – MAP CBioLit

During the third MAP cycle, the activity of the Lithuanian MAP will be focused on the topic "Entrepreneurship and social economy, just transition, including sustainable value chains" (topic 4). This topic is a follow-up of the previous topic "Change in production and diversification of the rural economy" covered by eight SHERPA MAPs in 2021, including Lithuanian MAP "CBioLit". It is related to the area of action "Prosperous rural areas" of the Long Term Vision for rural areas and it covers issues related to employment, reskilling, upskilling, entrepreneurship, short supply chains/sustainable value chains. This topic can build on recent research projects such as FOX, ROBUST, MOVING, RUBIZMO, LIVERUR, RURACTION, SIMRA, NEWBIE or RURITAGE.

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The NETHERLANDS – MAP Greenport Genderland

In 2020, this MAP worked on the “Orchard of the future” to form an idea of the outlook of fruit farms in the region as result of the many developments. In 2021, the focus of the MAP changed to the effects of climate change, especially on water availability and management. Climate change results in (more) dry periods, periods with high temperatures, extreme rainfall (excess water), and so on. This is a challenge for fruit growing as it became clear that even in the River Region in Gelderland, water can sometimes be a scarce resource. Despite the fact that the area of fruit orchards has been more or less stable for the last 20 years, the amount of water needed per hectare increases. For competitive fruit cultivation, water is essential. To secure the availability of sufficient water of good quality into the future, without problems caused by extreme weather events, action is needed. This can vary from actions on individual fruit farms to activities at regional level. Fruit growers can take the lead, but they need to work with other stakeholders to be able to reach their aims. In a MAP, such interaction between fruit growers and relevant stakeholders can be facilitated. This will also help position action plans of fruit growers in relation to wider efforts in the region to address (anticipated) climate-change effects. In 2021 the first set-up of an “Action plan” was made. The MAP wants to continue with this in 2022.

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POLAND – MAP Zielone Sąsiedztwo

In the third MAP cycle the MAP Zielone Sąsiedztwo will focus on “entrepreneurship, social economy, just transition and sustainable value chains” (topic 4) in Mazowieckie region. The MAP aims to put forward recommendations for policy-makers related to the listed issues to enable realisation of the vision for rural areas in the region by 2040. This was presented by MAP members in the MAP’s Position Paper during the first MAP cycle and the issues addressed in relation to rural economy diversification as discussed in the second MAP cycle.

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PORTUGAL – MAP Alqueva

In a region that has seen a huge change in its productive structure, with the installation of recent projects with scale and profitability, as a result of public investment in irrigation, and which is subject to increasing pressure from desertification, it is challenging to assure a correct land-use planning in the context of climate change. The platform provides a unique opportunity for stakeholders to engage, discuss the main issues and find ways forward in a comprehensive manner. The platform has been analysing research and policy initiatives that have been developed in the last two decades, developing foresight exercises, proposing new tools and rural research policies and promoting the engagement of regional and national institutions with shared common objectives.

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PORTUGAL – MAP Rural Portugal

MAP Rural PT, located in the Centro Region of Portugal, had the opportunity to work with local agents (policy, society and science) in the strategic vision for this region, focused on the European discussion topic “Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas”, with the identification of the main needs, challenges and opportunities combined with the main local action policies. In the third cycle, the MAP will focus on “Digitalisation and smart ruralities” (topic 2).

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ROMANIA – MAP Rural Transylvania

In Romania, the European Rural Development Network (ERDN) – Institute of Agricultural Economics of the Romanian Academy coordinates the Multi-Actor Platform Rural Transylvania. This platform operates in the West, North-West and Centre regions of the country. The Romanian Institute of Agricultural Economics facilitates the activities of the platform. Some of the challenges in rural Transylvania are the demographic shift, high number of small (subsistence) farms, low integration of small farms in agri-food chains, lack of infrastructure and basic services, and high agricultural dependence of peripheral rural communities. The platform aims to guiding strategic thinking among stakeholders for designing sustainable short value chains, through the integration of small and medium size farmers and other rural enterprises in sustainable food and value chains and building of urban-rural sustainable links.

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SLOVENIA – MAP Svarun

In Slovenia, the Biotechnical faculty of the University of Ljubljana coordinates the 'Multi-Actor Platform SVARUN'. The platform operates at a national level, building on previous cooperation with national stakeholders and engagement in the advisory council of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry. Additional stakeholders are engaged as appropriate for specific themes based on their roles in the agricultural policy-making process. The challenges in the Slovenian rural areas are depopulation, climate change, conservation of natural resources, animal welfare and nutritional trends, and food waste. The platform has been working on these challenges approaching topics related to rural value chains, digitalisation, rural cooperation, innovation in agriculture, sustainable animal husbandry and strengthening the knowledge and innovation system. The platform has been taking stock of relevant evidence for current and future developments in the fields of agriculture, natural resources and rural society relevant to national agricultural policy in the frame of the CAP. The aim is to establish the practice of combining scientific research and stakeholder views to form evidence-based policy in a mature policy cycle. In the third cycle, the MAP will focus on "social issues in rural areas" (topic 1).

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SPAIN – MAP IDRA

In northeastern Spain, the Polytechnic University of Madrid (UPM) and the Research Centre for the Management of Agricultural and Environmental Risks (CEIGRAM-UPM) coordinate the 'Multi-Actor Platform Innovation in rural development in Aragon' (IDRA). The MAP aims to have a good representation of all stakeholders and interests. The Aragon region is characterised by low population density and depopulation, unemployment, poor infrastructure and services, and an increasing proportion of men in rural areas because of the outmigration of women. This leads to the prioritisation of the following challenges: service provision for all rural people (transport, healthcare, education, housing), gender balance and opportunities for young people in rural areas, and improving the quality of life. The objective of the platform is to generate knowledge and create networks seeking synergies between various policy areas in order to contribute to vibrant rural areas. The third cycle will focus on the "Social dimension of rural areas" (topic 1) paying particular attention on how to make rural areas attractive for young and female citizens. The MAP will analyse topics related to access to housing, commercial facilities and land; access to services; and generational renewal in various economic sectors.

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SPAIN – MAP Galician Rural Interfaces

In the Spanish region of Galicia, the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) facilitates the Multi-Actor Platform Galician Rural Interfaces. This regional platform uses the Galician Association of Local Action Groups (GALAG) as support and a starting point. The region faces typical challenges of peripheral regions in Europe, such as rural depopulation and aging, and the abandonment of farmland. Its bioclimatic conditions characterise Galicia as prone to forest fire risk and scenarios of climate change indicate that the situation will worsen. The platform will focus on the following topics: employment and income generation, provision of infrastructures and services, and sustainable and inclusive land management. Specifically, in 2022 the work of the MAP will focus on the topic “Social dimension of rural areas” (topic 1). These topics will be addressed considering the diversity of the region, where the territorial dynamics lead to three differentiated rural kinds: a rural immersed in a very advanced process of abandonment, an active rural with a strong presence of agricultural land uses and a significant livestock specialization, and a last area where the urban-forest interface predominates.

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UNITED KINGDOM – MAP River Dee Catchment

Each year the MAP chooses a topic to focus on for deliberating and formulating positions. This has been done to align with the strategic objectives of the Dee Catchment Partnership, with a particular focus on the theme of tackling the climate emergency. The topics to date have been in collaboration with the Rural Scotland MAP, reflecting the broad nature of the topics, and links across scales from that of the catchment and Scotland more broadly. Those topics were: a “Long Term Vision for Rural Areas by 2040” for the first cycle, in collaboration with the Rural Scotland MAP, and “Climate Change and Environmental Sustainability” for the second cycle, in collaboration with the Rural Scotland MAP. For the third cycle, the MAP River Dee Catchment will focus on the topic of “Land management in the context of climate change” (topic 3), in collaboration with the Rural Scotland MAP.

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UNITED KINGDOM – MAP Rural Scotland

Each year the MAP chooses a topic to focus on for deliberating and formulating positions. For the first two cycles, the topics addressed were “Long Term Vision for Rural Areas by 2040” (first cycle) and “Climate Change and Environmental Sustainability” (second cycle), both in collaboration with MAP River Dee Catchment. A similar approach will be followed in the third cycle, where MAP Rural Scotland will work in collaboration with MAP River Dee Catchment on the topic of “Land management in the context of climate change” (topic 3).

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3. Composition of the MAPs

In SHERPA, the MAPs aim to include actors from the spheres of Science, Society and Policy, in order to ensure the democratisation of knowledge and influence over those policies and topics, which will be discussed in each cycle (Slätmo et al. 2020). Each MAP should aim to involve at least ten active members, as well as a Facilitator and a Monitor from the SHERPA national partner. External stakeholders can be invited to participate in activities on an ad-hoc basis.

It is important not to have a too narrow view of the three spheres, examples of which are as of below:

- i) **Science:** researchers with national or regional knowledge of rural areas. The researchers should have expertise in rural development, agriculture or the bio-economy or other rural topics of relevance to the regional MAP. Researchers identified should be credible, with established track record in the topic;
- ii) **Society:** representatives from the civil society, NGOs, business and farmer organisations, local citizens;
- iii) **Policy:** elected politicians or officials in public authorities at national, regional or local level.

Based on the analysis of DAPs for the third MAP cycle, the composition of the SHERPA MAPs is shown in Figure 3 for the first-round MAPs and in Figure 4 for newly established ones. With regard to the latter, it is worth highlighting that many MAPs declared being (at the time of writing) in the process of establishing the platform, and therefore still uncertain about the precise composition and size of their membership. At the onset of the third cycle, some MAPs were therefore only able to indicate approximate numbers in their DAPs, while others managed to provide already detailed lists of the names and affiliation of their membership (e.g. MAP CBioLit, MAP PACA Sud, MAP Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée).

The establishment phase has been identified by Potters et al. (2021) as a crucial stage for defining the MAP's composition, with attempts to strike a balance between an accurate and representative selection and avoiding too many actors. Opportunities for adjusting and enhancing the composition of the MAPs are however available to Facilitators and Monitors also while running the MAPs (Potters et al., 2021).

Figure 3 – Composition of the 21 first-round MAPs (%) Figure 4 – Composition of newly established MAPs (%)

A detailed account of each MAP’s composition is provided in Table 4 where absolute numbers and proportions of actors from each type of target communities are available. The colour assigned to cells show features either significantly below (violet: lower than 24%) or above (yellow: higher than 42%) one third of components (33%) (white cells).

Table 4 - Proportions of members of 41 MAPs per target community of actor (society, science and policy). Red box: below 25%; Yellow box: above 42%. Source: authors’ own elaboration from DAPs. NA: data not available. MAPs from no. 22 to 41 are newly established ones.

ID	MAP	Country	Science	Society	Policy	Tot	% of components		
							science	society	policy
1	VENUS	CZ	4	5	5	14	29	36	36
2	RURAL TRANSYLVANIA	RO	3	5	3	11	27	45	27
3	ZIELONE Sąsiedztwo	PL	6	8	3	17	35	47	18
4	SVARUN	SL	4	8	3	15	27	53	20
5	DENMARK	DK	3	9	6	18	17	50	33
6	EMILIA ROMAGNA	IT	5	5	7	17	29	29	41
7	IDRA	SP	4	4	2	10	40	40	20
8	TUSCANY	IT	5	6	7	18	28	33	39
9	CBioLit	LT	7	7	4	18	39	39	22
10	ALQUEVA	PT	6	9	6	21	29	43	29
11	RURAL-PT	PT	8	6	6	20	40	30	30
12	SCHLESWIG-HOLSTEIN	GE	3	9	3	15	20	60	20
13	SUOMI	FI	4	4	4	12	33	33	33
14	PACA	FR	9	6	16	31	29	19	52
15	GREENPORT	ND							
	GELDERLAND		2	8	5	15	13	53	33
16	GALICIAN RURAL	SP							
	INTERFACES		3	10	4	17	18	59	24
17	SOUTH AGEAN	GR	1	6	3	10	10	60	30
18	RIVER DEE CATCHMENT	UK	3	7	3	13	23	54	23
19	RURAL SCOTLAND	UK	3	7	4	14	21	50	29
20	HUNGARIAN AKIS	HU	8	7	10	25	32	28	40
21	BULGARIA	BG	2	6	2	10	20	60	20
22	VITAL VILLAGES	NL	3	5	3	11	27	45	27
23	CLIMATE PROOF								
	RURALITIES (P10	NL							
	NETWORK)		6	6	10	22	27	27	45
24	ESTONIA	EE	3	7	4	14	21	50	29
25	HUNGARIAN RURAL	HU							
	PROSPERITY MAP		6	6	5	17	35	35	29
26	IASI	RO	5	7	3	15	33	47	20
27	HUNGARIAN LAND-USE	HU							
	PLANNING FOR CN		6	5	6	17	35	29	35
28	ARGES	RO	5	7	4	16	31	44	25
29	CFV (CLIMATICALLY	CZ							
	FRIENDLY VILLAGE)		5	15	5	25	20	60	20
30	NORBOTTEN	SE	2	8	4	14	14	57	29
31	CASENTINO	IT	5	5	4	14	36	36	29
32	MONTAGNA TOSCANA	IT							
	(MOVING)		6	18	8	32	19	56	25
33	ZACHODNIOPOMORSKIE	PL	4	6	1	11	36	55	9
34	WALLONIA	BE	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
35	SOCIAL	BG							
	INFRASTRUCTURE		2	6	3	11	18	55	27

36	PYR-MED	FR	4	6	4	14	29	43	29
37	CENTRAL GREECE	GR	1	5	4	10	10	50	40
38	PELOPONNESE	GR	1	6	1	8	13	75	13
39	BIESZCZADY	PL	3	6	3	12	25	50	25
40	SW (SOUTHWEST ALENTEJO)	PT	7	8	8	23	30	35	35
41	NIENBURG	DE	2	6	3	11	18	55	27
TOTAL			169	280	189	638	26	44	30

The reflection on Table 4 requires a few preliminary comments. Each MAP represents a network, either at local, regional or national level, which is a first element of diversification and may as such affect the number of actors involved. A balance among the three groups of actors is generally pursued. However, specificities related to contexts and objectives for each MAP may suggest different approaches and proportions among the three groups. Besides, balance does not necessarily mean an equal numbers of members from each group. In particular, the societal sphere gathers a diversified range of actors, which require specific representation. As explained in more detail below in this section, this reflects the higher number of actors witnessed for this group in most MAPs.

Quantitative data on target communities represented in the MAPs constitute important pieces of information; however, not all members have the same weight, and their level of engagement in the MAP's activities may be different. This implies the possibility that a MAP be strongly based onto one of the three groups (Science, Society, or Policy) beyond the actual percentage of members in that group.

In addition, the representativeness of each actor listed in the DAPs varies from one category to another: one farmer counts as one singular member, whereas a cooperative union (e.g. in the MAP Svarun) or a LEADER Local Action Group (e.g. in the MAP IDRA) are collective actors with a potentially higher level of representativeness (not necessarily more relevant: also individual experiences can have a key role).

A further element of complexity may arise when considering whether individuals belonging to organisations, businesses or public authorities participate in the MAP's activities representing only themselves or the institutions to which they are affiliated.

In 2022, about **630 people are expected to be involved as members of the 41 MAPs**. A general overview suggests a good level of representativeness of the three spheres, with a majority of societal actors, and an almost even share for Science and Policy. Compared with the situation described at the outset of Phase I in 2020 (Mazzocchi et al., 2020³), the balance has improved in terms of the number of MAPs showing similar shares of members from the three spheres. This balance may be intended as a result of the MAPs' ability to ensure inclusiveness of a diversity of views and expertise.

The **actors belonging to the Society sphere outnumber both Policy and Science in most cases**, accounting for 44% of the total. Looking at the cases highlighted (yellow cells); societal actors represent 50% of more of the total number of participants in 19 MAPs. Except for one single case, the share of the Society group is always at least near to 30%. This prevalence possibly reflects a special attention paid to the involvement of civil society and specific stakeholder groups, but also to the higher heterogeneity of this sphere compared to the others, requiring as such a diversified representation. This group may also include the hardest to reach, who often have to participate on a voluntary basis, and this may have led Facilitators to contact more entities in order to ensure an adequate coverage in case of withdrawals during the process. With respect to specific categories of stakeholders, the data available show that rural businesses are mainly

³ Reporting on the MAPs composition in 2020, Mazzocchi et al. (2020) envisaged the opportunity of ensuring an equal representation of actors along the three spheres of Science, Policy and Society. This seems to be fulfilled in Phase 2 by both current and newly established MAPs. For a comparison, see [Mazzocchi et al. \(2020\). Synthesis report of the initial Dynamic Action Plans for 20 Multi-Actor Platforms \(D6.1\)](#)

represented by farmers and other (rural) entrepreneurs, either as individuals or in associated form (i.e. cooperatives, farmers’ organisations). Local Action Groups, rural youth associations, NGOs and other civil society organisations are also frequently listed in the Society group.

Science is represented by 26% of total MAP members, being as such the “least” represented group. This group never exceeds 40% of components, a share reached in two cases (i.e. MAP Denmark and MAP Rural PT). The relatively low proportion of researchers had been noticed and reported as feedback during Phase I (Mazzocchi et al., 2020) and perhaps as consequence of this, the proportion has since increased. A stronger presence of the scientific community was then expected as consistent with the composition of the SHERPA partnership, with academic experts often in charge of promoting or coordinating the MAPs. The Science actor as an expert on the topic tend to have a different role in the MAP as compared to the Policy and Society actors. This role often can be satisfyingly fulfilled by one or two research members in the MAP.

Almost one third (30%) of the MAP members belong to the Policy sphere, with figures slightly higher than the scientific community. For Policy, the membership reflects the geographical scope of the MAP, in some cases with a balance between national, regional and local representatives, in others with a focus on the level of governance consistent with the area to which the platform refers.

The overall distribution along the three actor spheres is as shown in Figure 5, and is compared with that of the MAPs in Phase I (Figure 6) of the project. In 2020, approximately⁴⁵ 250 actors were expected to be involved in the 20 MAPs.

Figure 5 - Total composition of 41 MAPs in 2022 (%)

Figure 6 - Total composition of 20 MAPs in 2020 (%)

⁴ Not all MAPs indicated detailed membership of their MAPs.

⁵ In many cases only affiliations were identified and not specific individuals, in which cases it was assumed there would be 1 person for each affiliation.

4. Objectives of the MAPs

SHERPA aims to gather knowledge that contributes to the formulation of recommendations for future policies relevant to EU rural areas, by creating a Science-Policy-Society interface, which provides a hub for knowledge and policy. The MAPs are therefore the primary interfaces on which SHERPA relies to gather such knowledge from regional to the EU level, and as such, they contribute to the project's goals, that is to:

1. Map the main drivers of future trends and dynamics of EU rural areas;
2. Establish Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) as effective and sustainable Science-Society-Policy interfaces;
3. Create a shared knowledge base relevant to EU rural policy by taking stock of results of past and ongoing research projects;
4. Engage in a dialogue between citizens, researchers and policy-makers across EU territories;
5. Formulate recommendations linked to different scenarios for the development of modern rural policies at European, national and regional levels, as well as for the future rural research agenda.

All the MAPs have established one or more (range 1 to 6) objectives for the forthcoming cycle. An analysis of the DAPs was therefore performed by coding all the MAPs' individual objectives, in order to relate the variety of objectives to a set of homogeneous clusters. In addition, in view to assess the degree of alignment of the MAPs' activities with the objectives set by the project, an initial set of codes was derived from the latter.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 illustrate the results of the clustering for respectively first round and new MAPs, indicating the number of times that objectives belonging to each cluster are included in the DAPs. Six main clusters emerged from the analysis of first-round MAPs, and the same codes were later applied to the clustering of the new MAPs, to allow for comparisons. The analysis shows that, besides the clusters directly attributable to the project goals, the MAPs pursue specific objectives related to the necessity of developing 'recommendations for civil society and businesses', and 'policy review and analysis'.

Figure 7 - Clusters of MAPs' objectives for 21 current MAPs. Source: authors' own elaboration from DAPs.

Figure 8 - Clusters of MAPs objectives for 20 newly established MAPs. Source: authors' own elaboration from DAPs.

As can be expected, 'establishing platforms/tools' and 'engaging dialogue with actors' are objectives more frequently targeted by the new MAPs, but no other major differences are visible from a comparison between current and new MAPs. Indeed, the relevance of objectives related to "socio-economic territorial appraisal", "co-construction of policy recommendations" and "engaging dialogue with actors" is shared by both new and current MAPs. Looking at the detail of individual MAPs, Table 5 illustrates the different approaches for the definition of the MAP's objectives. Each triangle represents the specific cluster to which one or more objectives pertain: whereas some MAPs tend to focus on one specific type of goals (e.g. on co-construction of policy recommendations), others tend to diversify and aim for different types of goals.

Table 5 – Cluster of objectives targeted by each MAP. Clusters are identified by the colours in Figures 4 and 5: green for 'socio-economic territorial appraisal', grey for 'co-construction of policy recommendations', yellow for 'engaging dialogue with actors', orange for 'establishing platforms', purple for 'recommendations for civil society and business', blue for 'policy review and analysis'. New MAPs indicated in green. Source: authors' own elaboration from DAPs.

Country	Name of the MAP	Clusters of targeted objectives					
BELGIUM	MAP Atelier Centre Wallonie	▲		▲		▲	▲
BULGARIA	MAP Rural Mapping Bulgaria	▲	▲				
BULGARIA	MAP Social infrastructure	▲	▲				▲
CZECH REPUBLIC	MAP VENUS	▲	▲		▲		
CZECH REPUBLIC	MAP Climate Friendly Village (CFV)	▲					▲
DENMARK	MAP Denmark		▲				
ESTONIA	MAP Estonia		▲				
FINLAND	MAP Suomi		▲				
FRANCE	MAP PACA Sud				▲	▲	
FRANCE	MAP Pays Pyrénées Méditerranée		▲		▲		▲

D6.3 | SYNTHESIS REPORT OF DYNAMIC ACTION PLANS FOR 41 MULTI-ACTOR PLATFORMS

GERMANY	MAP Schleswig Holstein	▲	▲				
GERMANY	MAP Nienburg		▲		▲	▲	
GREECE	MAP South Aegean	▲	▲	▲			
GREECE	MAP Central Greece	▲	▲	▲		▲	
GREECE	MAP Peloponnese	▲	▲	▲		▲	
HUNGARY	MAP Hungarian AKIS	▲					
HUNGARY	MAP Land use planning for climate neutrality	▲					▲
HUNGARY	MAP Rural prosperity	▲					
ITALY	MAP Tuscany		▲	▲			
ITALY	MAP Casentino		▲	▲	▲		
ITALY	MAP Montagna Toscana (MOVING)	▲	▲				
ITALY	MAP Regione Emilia Romagna	▲	▲	▲			
LITHUANIA	MAP Circular Bio-economy MAP (CBioLit)	▲	▲				
NETHERLANDS	MAP Greenport Gelderland		▲			▲	▲
NETHERLANDS	MAP Vital villages		▲	▲			
NETHERLANDS	MAP Climate proof ruralities (P10 network)	▲		▲			
POLAND	MAP Zielone Sąsiedztwo	▲					▲
POLAND	MAP Zachodniopomorskie	▲	▲			▲	
POLAND	MAP Bieszczady MAP		▲	▲			
PORTUGAL	MAP Alqueva				▲		▲
PORTUGAL	MAP Rural Portugal				▲		▲
PORTUGAL	MAP SW Alentejo			▲	▲		▲
ROMANIA	MAP Rural Transylvania			▲			
ROMANIA	MAP Iași			▲	▲		
ROMANIA	MAP Argeș			▲	▲		
SLOVENIA	MAP SVARUN - Slovenian Agricultural and Rural Network for Dialogue	▲		▲			
SPAIN	MAP IDRA - Innovación en Desarrollo Rural de Aragón		▲	▲			
SPAIN	MAP Galician Rural Interfaces	▲					▲
SWEDEN	MAP Norbotten		▲				
UNITED KINGDOM	MAP Dee Catchment Partnership	▲		▲		▲	
UNITED KINGDOM	MAP Rural Scotland	▲	▲	▲		▲	

5. Overview of activities, methods and outcomes in the Multi-Actor Platforms

SHERPA produces policy recommendations based on specific topics deemed relevant to rural areas, to which each MAP contributes through their Position Papers on selected topics. The collective construction of the Position Paper hinges on a complex range of knowledge sources and analyses: in turn, the papers feed policy debates concerning European rural development and the EU research agenda for rural areas.

The diversity of approaches and methods, and the flexibility in running the process and adjusting activities are the cornerstone of SHERPA MAP cycles. The MAPs are invited to find their own way to serve the SHERPA purposes, by experimenting, co-designing and running the activities and methods that fit best the agenda and needs of their members.

The appraisal of the DAPs in relation to activities, outcomes and methods allowed an overview of the main strands of activities and expected outcomes. In this overview of the activities planned by the MAPs, the first emerging fact is the **difference between current MAPs continuing their activities in their third cycle, and the newly established MAPs, which have to first set the conditions for engaging a dialogue**. Notwithstanding this difference, most of the listed activities, and the rationale behind them, are common between the two groups.

With regard to current MAPs, many DAPs declare the need for adapting/renewing/strengthening the structure and the organisation of the MAP itself, including the co-optation of new members also in the light of the new topics and, in some cases, out of the necessity to replace missing/lost members from earlier cycles. The latter is in line with the **emphasis on the continuous assessment of the MAP's composition**, to make adjustments and improve the coverage and representativeness of the MAP members.

The new MAPs need to build up by identifying members, structures and procedures. Defining the MAP's architecture, arranging internal communication channels, setting main objectives, and deciding on the specific focus of action are also amongst the activities primarily carried out by the new MAPs.

In relation to the self-organisation of the work, some DAPs mention the preparation of the MAP cycle plan (or the new plan for the recent MAPs) as a unique activity aimed at the preparation of the final Position Paper. The production of **the Position Paper on the selected topic is indeed the core outcome** around which the MAPs activities are organised and described. In this regard, the mentioned activities can be roughly clustered as follows:

- producing discussion/inspiration papers;
- drafting a first version of the Position Paper;
- refining and building consensus on the Position Paper;
- validating and finalising the Position Paper.

Discussion Papers are meant to provide an informative background (on documents, policies, actions, regional context, and other relevant experiences) for the following steps towards the Position Paper, including feeding subsequent MAPs meetings and workshops.

From a more operational point of view, the activities presented in the DAPs can be distinguished, as shown below, between preparatory actions (including the harvesting of information and the exploration of opportunities) and the workshops, which represent the core of the MAP dialogue with stakeholders and territory at the different geographical levels.

Preparation and documentation

- collecting data and mapping relevant issues and stakeholders, through a desk analysis, in some cases making an inventory of the main topics of interest;

- harvesting knowledge from MAP members (often a first step in the process), supported by discussions engaged with other SHERPA partners;
- gathering information and opinions through face-to face meetings (in person or online), talks/interviews, also with the aim to prepare the steps (workshops/focus groups);
- exploring opportunities for cooperation with other pertinent projects and initiatives.

Engaging dialogue

- organising workshops and focus groups, often at regional or local level (in general at the geographical level most appropriate for the specific initiative) to share/confront knowledge, perspectives, experiences on the selected topic and in the light of drafting the Position Paper.

Considered together, these activities represent the aim of the MAPs to proceed collectively, and to progressively validate the emerging outcomes through open confrontations of different perspectives. In addition, the MAPs activities are conducted in an open exchange with their territories, according to the geographical scope of the MAP. When the focus is local or regional, the synergy with existing initiatives and partnerships, on which the MAP itself can hinge, can be particularly close. In some cases, the link with, and the contribution to, wider debates on rural visions at regional, national or even EU level are signalled explicitly. Some MAPs give prominence to activities such as communication, dissemination and valorisation of outcomes, emphasising the use of specific tools and channels targeting the different categories of recipients (initiatives varying from e-mails to regional conferences).

Finally, attention has been dedicated in a significant number of DAPs to the need for an evaluation of MAP activities, highlighting that feedbacks are expected to streamline the process and to keep the MAPs’ activities aligned with SHERPA objectives.

As methods are specifically concerned, Figure 9 shows how most MAPs have planned to use a mix of methods, combining in the first place desk-based research and analysis (25 MAPs) with (more or less informal) face-to-face meetings (22 MAPs). More specific methods applied include workshops, focus groups and other types of participatory tools, both online and face-to-face depending on the specific needs and capacities of MAP members and Facilitators (31 MAPs), followed by interviews and survey, both online and face-to-face. Tailored methods for communicating and disseminating on planned activities, events and outputs are highlighted in ten DAPs, varying according to the needs of the specific audiences. These figures are in line with methods applied in Phase I, when COVID-19-related restrictions required the MAPs to experiment with new ways and spaces of online engagement. The MAPs revealed creative and able to adapt to the changed conditions, allowing diverse actors and perspectives to be engaged in the dialogue.

Figure 9 - Methods used to carry out the MAP's activities (no. of MAPs). Source: authors' own elaboration from DAPs.

6. Final Remarks

The 41 Multi-Actor Platforms of SHERPA work on themes and issues relevant for rural areas and are characterised by a diversity of members, approaches, goals and actions. At month 31 (April 2022), the MAPs are at different stages of development, but all MAPs went through the process of drafting a Dynamic Action Plan (DAP) in the months December 2021 - February 2022. The DAP provided MAP Facilitators and members with a tool and space for starting their dialogue, by setting goals and sharing visions, planning activities, and communicating about the MAP.

This document provides an updated overview and systematic synthesis of key information drawn from the 41 DAPs compiled by SHERPA MAPs. The evidence gathered and recommendations are summarised as follows:

- Approximately 630 actors have been/are being identified, contacted, invited or already confirmed as members of the MAPs;
- On average, the MAPs are composed of 15 members;
- In relation to the three spheres of Science, Society and Policy addressed by the MAPs, 44% of expected and actual MAP members belong to Society, 26% to Science and 30% to Policy. This implies an imbalance in favour of civil society representatives, which can be explained by the higher heterogeneity and specific features of this actors' group;
- In the third cycle, nine MAPs will be working on the "Social dimension of rural areas" (topic 1), four MAPs on "Digitalisation and smart ruralities" (topic 2), while "Land-use management in the context of climate change" (topic 3) will involve 12 MAPs and "Entrepreneurship, social economy, just transition and sustainable value chains" (topic 4) will be addressed by 16 MAPs.
- The MAPs pursue objectives that are aligned to those of the SHERPA project, adding in some cases more specific goals to respond to specific needs of their areas and stakeholders. In particular, the most targeted goals are related to the "socio-economic territorial appraisal", followed by the "co-construction of policy recommendation" and "engaging dialogue with actors", which both new and current MAPs pursue in the first place. More specific objectives pertain to "policy review and analysis", "recommendation for civil society and business".
- In terms of activities planned for the third cycle, most are common to both new and current MAPs and revolve around a marked commitment towards the production of the MAP's Position Paper, intended as the main outcome of the MAP cycle.
- In operational terms, one main difference emerging between current and new MAPs pertains to the necessity, for the latter, to first set the conditions for engaging a dialogue with actors, whereas the former are considering adapting/renewing/strengthening the architecture of the MAP to the new cycle.
- The MAPs are planning to use combinations of different methods, encompassing both online and face-to-face settings. Desk-based research is in most cases accompanied by participatory methods, including different types of workshops and focus groups, followed by interviews and surveys. Ten MAPs are also planning to focus more on communication and dissemination, tailoring the methods applied to the specific needs of their audiences.

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Annex 1 – DAP template

Dynamic Action Plan Multi-Actor Platform | NAME OF THE MAP

This *Dynamic Action Plan* (DAP) illustrates the thematic focus, objectives and activities of the *Multi Actor Platform* (MAP) in Tuscany coordinated by the research group of agricultural and food economics at the University of Pisa. The facilitator of this MAP commits to the implementation of the activities and guiding the MAP to achieve outcomes specified in this DAP. Any deviations will be discussed with the MAP participants and MAP monitor.

Thematic focus, objectives and expected outcomes

Thematic focus

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Specific objectives

- ...
- ...
- ...

Through these objectives, the MAP aims to achieve the following outcomes:

- ...
- ...

Working methods and planned activities for the 2nd MAP cycle

Working methods

- ...
- ...
- ...

Planned activities for the 2nd MAP cycle

- *Activity 1*

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- *Activity 2*

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- *Activity N*

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ANNEX 1. Summary of the key information about the MAP

Key data	Description
Name and location of the MAP (country and region)	
Composition of the MAP	
Name and email of Facilitator	
Name and email of Monitor	
Valid period	
Key indicators (Eurostat data or data from you region)	
Date when DAP is drafted	

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